

DigiTala's questionnaire for upper-secondary language teachers on oral language skills

This questionnaire for teachers of foreign languages, Finnish or Swedish as second national language and Finnish or Swedish as second language and literature (S2) in general upper secondary schools is a part of the DigiTala research project (Academy of Finland 2019-2023 see website helsinki.fi/en/digitala).

We are using this questionnaire to map teachers' perceptions of the assessment of oral language skills. Participation in the study is optional. It takes 10-15 min. to reply. Every reply is important to us, thank you for participating!

By replying to the questionnaire, you give your permission to use your information in research. We will treat the information in confidence and anonymously. We are not asking for any identifying information, so we cannot give permission to check, change, or remove your answers later. Please see our privacy notice at helsinki.fi/en/digitala/privacy.

If you have any questions or you want to try the tool we are developing, please email anna.vonzansen@helsinki.fi or phone 0505292445.

I Background details

1. Which languages do you teach in upper secondary school? Select one or more alternatives.

- | | | |
|---|---|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Finnish as second national language (finska) | <input type="checkbox"/> Finnish as second language and literature (S2) | <input type="checkbox"/> Swedish as second national language |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Swedish as second language and literature (R2) | <input type="checkbox"/> English | <input type="checkbox"/> Spanish |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Italian | <input type="checkbox"/> Latin | <input type="checkbox"/> French |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Saami | <input type="checkbox"/> German | <input type="checkbox"/> Russian |
| <input type="checkbox"/> another language, which? | <input style="width: 200px; height: 30px;" type="text"/> | |

2. How long have you worked as a teacher?

- 0-1 year
- 2-5 years
- 6-10 years
- 11-15 years
- 16 years or more

3. Have you attended in-service training in oral language skills and the teaching of them?

- yes
- no

II Practices for assessing oral language skills

In this questionnaire, foreign languages include the courses in Finnish / Swedish as second (national) language. The following questions may not apply to all language teachers.

4. How much weight do you think the following dimensions should be given in the assessment of oral language skills in foreign languages? (Please reply on the scale 1 not at all – 5 very much)

	1	2	3	4	5
fluency (pauses, repetitions)	<input type="radio"/>				
pronunciation (intelligibility)	<input type="radio"/>				
extent of vocabulary and structures	<input type="radio"/>				
grammatical accuracy	<input type="radio"/>				
interaction skills	<input type="radio"/>				
communication according to target culture	<input type="radio"/>				
strategies of oral communication	<input type="radio"/>				

5. Have you asked your students to assess their oral language skills during your courses / study units (both obligatory and optional)?

- always
 sometimes
 never

The Finnish National Agency for Education has produced exam tasks for a course in oral language skills. These are available in an exam bank.

6. Have you used the tasks in the exam bank?

- yes
 no

Instead of an oral exam, the exam in oral language skills produced by the Finnish National Agency for Education can also be covered with other oral performances ([read more](#)).

7. Are you going to offer your students the possibility of oral performances?

- yes
 no
 I cannot say

The [Evolving Language Proficiency Scale](#) that is part of the National Core Curriculum for General Upper Secondary Education is an adaptation of the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFR).

8. How well do you think you can apply the proficiency scale of the curriculum when you are assessing oral skills? (Please reply on the scale 1 strongly disagree – 5 agree strongly)

	1	2	3	4	5
I think that I can apply it well.	<input type="radio"/>				

9. You may want to complement your replies on assessment practices (questions 4-8)

III The future: automated assessment of oral language skills

The DigiTala project is developing an application based on automatic speech recognition, which will assess speech samples automatically and give feedback to learners. The application could be used for practicing speaking and as a part of language teaching.

10. How do you feel about automated assessment of oral skills?

	1 very negative	2 quite negative	3 neutral	4 quite positive	5 very positive
My attitude to automated assessment	<input type="radio"/>				

11. What are the advantages and benefits of automated assessment?

12. What are the disadvantages and threats of automated assessment?

13. What would you like to ask about automated assessment?

If an oral part were to be included in the language tests of the Matriculation Examination, automated assessment could partially be used to support human assessment. No decisions have yet been made, however.

14. Should the language tests in the Matriculation Examination include an oral part? Please reply for all the languages and syllabi below, even if you do not teach them.

	yes	no
English (A)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Finnish / Swedish (B1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Swedish / Finnish (native-level)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Swedish / Finnish (A)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
German / French / Russian / Spanish (A)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
B2 and B3 languages	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Finnish (S2) / Swedish as second language and literature	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

15. Why should an oral part be included in the language tests of the Matriculation Examination?

16. Why should an oral part not be included in the language tests of the Matriculation Examination?

IV Your first impression of the DigiTala Moodle tool

The DigiTala project has created the first version of the Moodle tool for learners of Swedish and Finnish. The learners will respond to read-aloud and production tasks (3min) and will receive automated feedback on their speech. The system is available in Finnish, Swedish, and English.

17. Would you like to hear more about the DigiTala Moodle tool?

- Yes please, I want to hear more and watch the video (c. 3 min)
- Sorry, I do not have time to watch the video

Watch the video presentation of the DigiTala tool [using this link](#).

18. Based on the video, please give your views on the following statements.

	1 strongly disagree	2 disagree	3 neither agree nor disagree	4 agree	5 agree strongly
I would like to use this system frequently.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I find the system unnecessarily complex.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I think the system was easy to use.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I would need the support of a technical person to be able to use this system.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The various functions in this system are well integrated.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
There is too much inconsistency in this system.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Most people would learn to use this system very quickly.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I find the system very cumbersome to use.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I would feel very confident using the system.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

1 strongly disagree 2 disagree 3 neither agree nor disagree 4 agree 5 agree strongly

I would need to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system.

19. Questions and comments on the system

V Need for further education

20. In what areas of teaching and assessing oral language skills do you need further education? Select one or more alternatives.

- Aspects of oral language skills and the teaching of them, which?
- Using the proficiency scale in assessment
- Numerical assessment
- Giving students feedback
- Self-assessment
- Peer assessment
- Organising an oral exam
- Organising oral performances
- The technology for recording and saving speech
- Processing of personal data (speech is personal data)

21. Tell us more about your needs for further education

Submit

Thank you for your participation!
Read more about the [DigiTala tool](#).